

EVALUATION OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE SPECIAL FOSTER SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL PROGRAM IN DUMAI, RIAU PROVINCE, INDONESIA: CIPP EVALUATION MODEL

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Abstract

The responsibility of the government in improving the quality of education in Indonesia is to equalize the quality of education in Indonesia, local wisdom, and regional autonomy in the implementation of education. The Indonesian government has made the equal distribution of the quality of education through the establishment of the Special Foster Senior High School (SMA Binaan Khusus). This school has programs to improve the quality of teachers, improve the quality of adequate facilities and infrastructure, and improve the quality of students who have the potential to be nurtured and developed. This study aims to evaluate the implementation of programs in the SMA Binaan Khusus. The research method used is descriptive with a qualitative approach using the context, input, process, and product (CIPP) model. The results of the study indicate that the SMA Binaan Khusus has implemented its programs and has been used as an example and reference for another school.

Keywords: CIPP model, especially foster school, evaluation program, SMA Binaan Khusus

1. INTRODUCTION

Education is one of the efforts to build and improve the quality of human resources in the era of globalization. Education is the process of providing knowledge, training, and skills carried out in a place of learning to improve one's knowledge and skills (Thangeda & Baratiseng, 2016). Education functions to develop capabilities and shape the character and civilization of a dignified nation in the context of the intellectual life of the nation. Education is used as a provision of life that we can use to face global changes (Naziev, 2017). Quality education gives a person the ability and thinking power to be able to interpret things correctly.

The quality of education will affect a person's philosophical mind-set and lifestyle in making decisions in their lives. The quality of education will determine the quality of graduates produced by education implementers. The quality of education in Indonesia is still low compared to other countries. Low-quality education results in poor quality human resources and vice versa (Alifah, 2021). Education must be carried out to form quality human resources so that education becomes the responsibility of the community and government. The responsibility of the government in improving the quality of education in Indonesia is to equalize the quality of education in Indonesia, local wisdom, and regional autonomy in the implementation of education. Through local wisdom and regional autonomy, each region in Indonesia is expected to be able to realize education that is globally oriented and based on local

wisdom and regional autonomy (Handayani et al., 2019; Widodo, 2019). In regional autonomy, education autonomy can be carried out as a result of reforms that have been implemented. Become a political commitment since regional autonomy was enacted. Law Number 22 of 1999 concerning Regional Government has delegated the authority of the central government to regional governments to exercise autonomy in education. Educational autonomy is believed to be able to improve the quality of education, face the challenges that occur in the world of education, build a solid education system in the regions, democratize education with real and broad participation from the community, foster independence, accelerate services, and the potential of local resources in the region can be utilized optimally. For an educational advancement (Ayu, 2017; Darmadi, 2018; Jati & Bambang, 2019).

The Indonesian government has made various efforts to improve the quality of education, such as curriculum development programs, textbook procurement programs, school operational assistance, school-based quality improvement management programs, teacher quality improvement programs, and special foster school programs. The special foster school program has been established in 2003 in Dumai, Riau province, Indonesia. The first and only special foster school program in Indonesia is in Dumai. The special foster school program was developed by the Dumai education office which aims to improve the quality of education starting from Elementary, Junior High School, to Senior High School (SMA Binaan Khusus). The special foster school program was made by the Decree of the Mayor of Dumai, No. 318/DISDIKKO/2003. The SMA Binaan Khusus program has the status of a public school that is given priority as well as resource facilities which include a program to improve the quality of teachers, a program to improve the quality of school facilities, and infrastructure, and a program to improve the quality of students who has the potential to be nurtured and developed. If the SMA Binaan Khusus program is successful, it will be used as an example and a reference for other schools in Dumai as schools with a vision of excellence.

Based on the results of the National Examination scores in 2018/2019, the SMA Binaan Khusus is ranked 1st so it can be said that the SMA Binaan Khusus in Dumai has become the best compared to other Senior High Schools. The average value of the National Examination and Final Examination of the SMA Binaan Khusus in the last three years shows results above the minimum value and has increased. The number of students who continued to higher education in 2018/2019 was 128 people or 71% of the total number of students. In addition, the number of SMA Binaan Khusus students who continued their studies and were accepted into the top 10 State Universities from 2017 to 2019, amounted to 21 people. This study aims to evaluate the implementation of the SMA Binaan Khusus program in Dumai, Riau Province, Indonesia. This evaluation is a form of education system mechanism that aims to review the educational process that has been carried out for a certain period. In addition, the evaluation aims to understand, explore, and correct the educational process so that deficiencies that must be corrected and covered will be identified (Mahmudi, 2011; Darma, 2019; Irawan & Prasetyo, 2020; Ariawan et al., 2016; Singh, 2004). Educational evaluation is very much needed to realize a good education system and always improve itself by covering any shortcomings from time to time.

2. METHODOLOGY

This research was conducted at the SMA Binaan Khusus in Dumai, Riau Province, Indonesia. The research method is descriptive using a qualitative approach. In this study, researchers used the concept of a context, input, process, and product (CIPP) model (Stufflebeam & Shinkfield 1986). The object of research is the SMA Binaan Khusus, the principal, the deputy principal, teachers, and the Dumai education office. Data collection techniques were carried out by observation, interviews, and documentation. Observation tools were used in the form of field notes and interviews and the data were analyzed using the CIPP evaluation model analysis.

3. RESULTS

The Mayor of Dumai has given priority and resource facilities to the SMA Binaan Khusus, namely teacher quality improvement programs, improving the quality of adequate facilities and infrastructure programs, and improving the quality of students who have the potential to be fostered and developed program. The following are the programs that have been evaluated by the research team at the SMA Binaan Khusus in Dumai, Riau Province, Indonesia.

Teacher quality improvement program

The SMA Binaan Khusus is a school with an insight into excellence, trying to realize the Human Resources of Dumai that are qualified, faithful, and able to compete in the Globalization Era. The vision of SMA Binaan Khusus is to realize superior, skilled, polite, and Malay-cultured human resources. In the quality improvement program four indicators have been evaluated by the research team, namely a) implementing a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) with superior schools at home and abroad, b) English language training, c) information technology-based learning training, and d) continue education to a higher level (Table 1).

Table 1: The Result of the Teacher Quality Improvement Program

Implement MoU with superior schools at home and abroad		
CIPP Model	Content	Results
Context	Implementation of the MoU with superior schools at home and abroad.	SMA Binaan Khusus has carried out this program
Input	Human resources, funding, and methods in this program	The school committee, and the Dumai city education office. Source of funds Dumai city government.
Process	Facilitate participants in the program. The involvement of participants in the implementation of the program	Schools and teachers provide support for the implementation of this program.
Product	Results of this program	Improvement of the quality of services to the community. Increase insight, and experience, and motivate teachers in improving their competence. Increase student motivation in learning and get better educational services.
English training		
CIPP Model	Content	Results

Context	Improving the quality of teachers through English language training.	This program has been implemented by the SMA Binaan Khusus
Input	Human resources, funding, and methods in this program	The school principal, the deputy for curriculum, the deputy for quality improvement, the school treasurer, and the English teacher. In terms of funding, everything comes from school funds
Process	Facilitate participants in the implementation of these programs	The school provides full facilitation and support to the teacher to improve their quality or competence.
Product	Results of this program	English teachers can improve their quality and competence, this also affects the quality of learning.
ICT-based learning training		
CIPP Model	Content	Results
Context	Improving the quality of teachers through ICT-based learning training.	The SMA Binan Khusus has improved the quality of teachers through ICT-based learning training.
Input	Human resources and funding improve the quality of teachers through ICT-based learning training.	Teachers, education staff, and staff. Activity costs come from school funds
Process	Facilitate participants in the implementation of this program.	In the process, the school provides full facilitation and support to educators and education staff to improve their quality or competence.
Product	Results of this program	Teachers can operate computers, create multimedia learning media, create blogs, use Google Classroom, and do online learning.
Continuing education to a higher level		
CIPP Model	Content	Results
Context	Facilitate the improvement of the academic qualifications of teachers.	The teacher has increased the teacher's academic qualification
Input	Improved teacher's academic qualifications and given a fee	The SMA Binaan Khusus and the Dumai city government comply with applicable terms and regulations.
Process	Facilitate the improvement of teachers' academic qualifications	The SMA Binaan Khusus provide support to teachers who want to improve their academic qualifications, such as moral motivation, and simplify all kinds of administration needed.
Product	Results of this program	The teachers have increased their academic qualifications and teacher competencies so that they can build quality and improve learning for students.

The research team has evaluated the implementation of the MoU with superior schools at home and abroad through interviews with the principal, deputy head of quality management, Dumai city education office, and the school committee. The results of the interview are supported by the results of documentation and observations, namely documents that prove the implementation of MoU activities with superior schools at home and abroad in the form of archives of minutes, letters of agreement, certificates, and souvenirs about the MoU with

superior schools at home and abroad. The MoU activities between the SMA Binaan Khusus and excellent domestic and foreign schools were carried out well. In terms of input, the parties involved in this activity are the school, the school committee, and the Dumai education office. Funding for the MoU comes from the Dumai government, committees, and PCR funds from companies in Dumai. In the facilitation process, schools provide support for the implementation of collaboration with superior schools at home and abroad. The results of the MoU implementation between the SMA Binaan Khusus and superior schools at home and abroad are 1) as an evaluation of the school to improve the quality of services to the community, 2) to increase insight, experience, and motivate teachers to improve their competence, 3) increase student motivation in learning and get better education services, and 4) stakeholders can play a more active role as advisor, support, and control for strengthening the SMA Binaan Khusus program.

The research team has evaluated the implementation of the English language training program for teachers through interviews with the principal, deputy head of quality management, deputy head of curriculum, English teachers, and school treasurers. In the context of the SMA Binaan Khusus, they have not improved the quality of teachers through independent English language training for all teachers but have been individually by sending English teachers to attend training. Context evaluation plays a role in providing rational reasons for a program to be implemented. In the context evaluation, there are program objectives, policies for implementing the institution's vision and mission, relevant conditions, and needs assessment. The school provides transportation costs by school regulations and policies. The school provides full facilitation and support to educators to improve their quality or competence. The result is that English teachers can improve their quality and competence, this also affects the quality of learning in the SMA Binaan Khusus.

The implementation of the ICT-based learning training program was obtained from the results of interviews with the principal, the deputy principal for quality management, the deputy principal for the curriculum, and the school treasurer. The results of the evaluation show that the SMA Binaan Khusus has improved the quality of teachers through ICT-based learning training. The training activities carried out included the creation of ICT-based learning media, the creation of a Blog, and the use of Google Classroom, as well as training on the creation of online learning applications. The Human Resources involved are all school residents, namely educators and education staff, and IT expert resource persons. In terms of funding, everything comes from school funds to improve the quality of educators. In the process, the school provides full facilitation and support to educators and education staff to improve their quality or competence. The result is that teachers can operate computers, create multimedia learning media, create blogs, use Google Classroom, and conduct online learning during the Covid-19 pandemic. The implementation of the SMA Binaan Khusus program on improving the academic qualifications of educators and education staff to a higher level of education was obtained from the results of interviews with the school principal, the deputy head of the quality management section, and one of the teachers who took part in improving their academic qualifications. The evaluation results contained in Table 1 show that the SMA Binaan Khusus has facilitated the improvement of teacher academic qualifications, namely by providing

support for moral motivation and easiness in administration. Tuition fees come from independent fees and scholarships from the Dumai government. The results of increasing the qualifications of teachers, which can improve the quality of schools. This will also be the motivation and competence of teachers to increase to build the quality of the SMA Binaan Khusus. If the teachers have the motivation and potential, this will affect the learning process for students. Teachers in the digital era can improve and express themselves in the field of developing learning media and understanding the knowledge that will be shared with students.

Improve the quality of adequate facilities and infrastructure program

In this program four indicators will be evaluated by the research team, namely (a) providing ICT-based learning facilities in the classroom, (b) providing digital library facilities, c) providing facilities and infrastructure that support the improvement of teacher professionalism, and (d) providing facilities and infrastructure to develop the academic and non-academic potential of students (Table 2).

Table 2: The Result of Improving the Quality of Adequate Facilities and Infrastructure Program

ICT-based learning facilities in the classroom		
CIPP Model	Content	Results
Context	Procurement of ICT-based learning facilities in the classroom	The procurement of ICT-based learning facilities in each class has been carried out, namely by installing a projector in each class.
Input	Human resources, costs, and methods in procuring ICT-based learning facilities in the classroom.	Dumai city government, parents, and school operational funds are involved in procuring ICT-based learning facilities in the classroom
Process	Facilitate the procurement of ICT-based learning facilities in the classroom	The facility process has not been maximized because many projectors in each class are damaged so they cannot be used for the learning process.
Product	The results of the procurement of ICT-based learning facilities in the classroom	The projector in every class is damaged so it cannot be used for learning
Digital library facilities		
CIPP Model	Content	Results
Context	Program for procurement of digital library facilities	The SMA Negeri Binaan Khusus has a library but it has not been managed digitally.
Input	Human resources, costs, and methods in the procurement of digital library facilities.	The books come from purchases and donations from well-wishers. The source of funds comes from school operational funds.
Process	Facilitating the procurement of digital libraries and digital library management	The SMA Binaan Khusus facilitate the needs of the library and its management manually
Product	The results of the implementation of the digital library program	Textbooks and supporting books in various subject areas are available. Students' reading interest increases and can help teachers and students in adding references to learning activities.
Facilities and infrastructure that support increasing teacher professionalism		
CIPP Model	Content	Results

Context	Provide facilities that support the improvement of teacher professionalism.	The SMA Binaan Khusus has provided facilities and infrastructure to improve teacher professionalism.
Input	Human resources, funding, and methods in procuring facilities that support teacher professionalism improvement.	The implementation of this program involves the Dumai city government and the parents of students. Sources of funds come from the Dumai city government, parents, and school operational funds. For its operations using school operational funds.
Process	The process of procuring and utilizing facilities that support the improvement of teacher professionalism	This program has not been maximized because several facilities cannot be utilized (damaged). Infrastructure can already be used properly for school activities. This activity involved schools, the community, parents, and the Dumai city government.
Product	Results of the program	Can improve the smoothness of activities that can support teacher professionalism.
Provide facilities to develop student's academic and non-academic potential.		
CIPP Model	Content	Results
Context	Procurement of facilities to develop the academic and non-academic potential of students.	This program has been well implemented
Input	Human resources, funding, and methods in procuring facilities to develop the academic and non-academic potential of students.	The implementation of this program involves the Dumai city government and the parents of students. Sources of funds come from the Dumai city government, parents, and school operational funds. For its operations using school operational funds.
Process	The process of procuring and utilizing facilities to develop the academic and non-academic potential of students.	The process of facilitation of the facilities has not been maximized because some facilities cannot be utilized (damaged). The infrastructure can be used properly for school activities. The parties involved are the school, the community, the parents of students, and the Dumai city government.
Product	Benefits of facilitating the means to develop the academic and non-academic potential of students.	The SMA Binaan Khusus has adequate facilities and infrastructure so that it can increase the potential of students academically and non-academic.

The implementation of the ICT-based learning facilities program in the classroom has been evaluated by the research team (Table 2). The results of the evaluation show that the SMA Binaan Khusus has procured ICT-based learning facilities in each class. Namely by installing projectors in each class. Sources of procurement funds come from the assistance of the Dumai government, students' parents, and school operational funds. The facilitation process has not been maximized because many projectors in each class are damaged so that they cannot be used for the learning process. The parties involved in this case should be the principal and the deputy for facilities and infrastructure to repair or replace the damaged units. If the projector's conditions in each class are in good condition, it will be able to be utilized optimally so that it will improve the quality of education. The facilities and infrastructure owned by the school are a supporting factor for the implementation of school programs, especially learning activities carried out by teachers.

The facilities and infrastructure owned by the school must be managed properly, with the aim that if the school community wants to need or use it, then the facilities and infrastructure are ready to use. The SMA Binaan Khusus library has not been carried out as digital. The school facilitates well what the library needs. Books were procured from purchases and donations from well-wishers. The source of management funds comes from schools, namely using school operational funds. The result is the availability of textbooks and supporting books in various subject areas to help teachers and students to get additional references in learning activities while also increasing reading interest for students in the SMA Binaan Khusus in Dumai. Library management at SMA Binaan Khusus is done manually. This means that the procurement program for digital library facilities has not been implemented by the planned program. The SMA Binaan Khusus has provided facilities and infrastructure to improve teacher professionalism. Teacher competence in welcoming the industrial revolution 4.0 began to increase mastery of ICT-based learning media. These facilities and infrastructure include places of worship, science laboratories, computer laboratories, libraries, learning resource centers, information and counseling centers, art halls, halls, sports fields, and learning huts. Sources of procurement funds come from the assistance of the Dumai government, parents of students, and operations using school operational funds.

The process of facilitation of the facilities has not been maximized because several facilities cannot be utilized (damaged). As for the infrastructure, it can be used properly for school activities. The result is that the SMA Binaan Khusus has the facilities and infrastructure that can be used to improve the quality of the teaching staff and can also be used for activities that can support teacher professionalism and improve the quality of the SMA Negeri Binaan Khusus in Dumai.

The evaluation results based on Table 2 show that the SMA Binaan Khusus has facilitated facilities and infrastructure to develop the potential of students, both academic and non-academic. Among them are places of worship, science laboratories, computer laboratories, libraries, learning resource centers, information and counseling centers, art halls, halls, sports fields, and learning huts. Sources of procurement funds come from the assistance of the Dumai government, parents of students, and for its operations using school operational funds. The process of facilitation of the facilities has not been maximized because several facilities cannot be utilized (damaged). The result is that the SMA Binaan Khusus has facilities and infrastructure that can be used to increase the potential of students academically and non-academic.

Improve the quality of students who have the potential to be fostered and developed program

In this program, three indicators will be evaluated, namely (a) preparing students to achieve academic and non-academic achievements at national and international levels, (b) conducting habituation of noble character through religious activities, and (c) holding a talent tests of interest in admissions the new student (Table 3).

Table 3: The result of improving the quality of students who have the potential to be fostered and developed program

Preparing students in achieving academic and non-academic achievements at national and international levels.		
CIPP Model	Content	Results
Context	Prepare students to achieve national and international academic and non-academic achievements.	The SMA Binaan Khusus has prepared students to achieve national and international academic and non-academic achievements.
Input	Human resources, funding, and methods in preparing students to achieve academic and non-academic achievements at national and international levels.	The parties involved in this activity are teachers. The source of funding comes from school funds. Principals empower teachers who are in their fields.
Process	Facilitation in preparing students to achieve national and international academic and non-academic achievements.	The principal has provided support for this program.
Product	Results of this program	Students excel academically and non-academic.
Holding noble morals habituation through religious activities		
CIPP Model	Content	Results
Context	Habituation of noble character through religious activities.	The SMA Binaan Khusus has carried out the habituation of noble character through religious activities.
Input	Human resources, funding, and methods in habituation of noble character through religious activities.	Human resources involved in this activity are school principals, teachers (especially religious teachers), lecturers from outside the school, and students. Funding for this activity comes from the SMA Binaan Khusus funds. The method used in this activity is to empower all teachers and students as well as lecturers from outside the school.
Process	Facilitation for the habituation of students' noble character	The principal provides support in the habituation of students' noble character through religious activities.
Product	Results of program activities	All students of the SMA Binaan Khusus have good morals.
Aptitude test interest in new student admission		
CIPP Model	Content	Results
Context	Aptitude test interest in new student admission	The interest aptitude test program in new student admissions has been implemented
Input	Human resources, funding, and methods in	Human resources involved in the admission of new students are principals,

	the implementation of the aptitude test interest in the admission of new students	teachers, administrators, and school operators. Funding in this program is school funds. The method of implementing this program is zoning, achievement, affirmation, and transfer of parents/teacher children.
Process	Facilitation and involvement of participants in the aptitude test of interest in new student admissions.	The principal fully supports this new student admission activity through the new student admissions committee and involves all school parties.
Product	Results of program activities	New students are accepted through zoning, achievement, affirmation, and parent/child transfer routes.

The results of the study in Table 3 show that the SMA Binaan Khusus have implemented programs to prepare students to achieve academic and non-academic achievements at national and international levels. The principal empowers teachers by their fields in preparing students to take part in academic and non-academic activities.

The source of funding for these activities comes from school funds. The principal provides facilitation support in all activities to prepare students to achieve academic and non-academic achievements. The result is that the SMA Binaan Khusus achieved academic and non-academic achievements. This can be seen from the number of students who are accepted at the best universities in Indonesia.

Implemented a noble character habituation program through religious activities. There are several parties involved in this activity, namely the principal, teachers (especially religion teachers), lecturers from outside the school, and students of the SMA Binaan Khusus in Dumai. Funding for this activity is sourced from the SMA Binaan Khusus funds. In the facilitation process, the principal provides full support for the habituation of noble character through religious activities. The result is that the students of the SMA Binaan Khusus have good morals.

The SMA Binaan Khusus no longer conduct interest aptitude tests in the acceptance of new students. New student admissions now use the zoning route, achievement path, affirmations, and transfer of parents or teachers who teach at SMA Binaan Khusus. For the achievement path, it is required to have the highest certificate/charter in terms of academic and non-academic at international, national, provincial, and district levels. Funding for the acceptance of new students is school funds and subsidies from the government for affirmations. In this regulation, the school cannot select potential students. In the implementation process, all teachers are actively involved. With the acceptance of new students with the zoning system, the result is that the SMA Binaan Khusus cannot attract students who have the potential to be fostered and developed.

4. DISCUSSION

Education lasts a lifetime and becomes a necessity of human life from beginning to end. Education can be used as a provision for life to achieve a better life. Is education necessary for everyone? The answer is not about whether it is necessary or not but how the education can be implemented, what must be achieved (objectives), and how the implementers (educators) work. Education must be obtained by everyone so that they can think intellectually and can interpret things correctly. Education is the development of skills and knowledge as a result of practice, learning, and experience. According to the Indonesian education leader Dewantara (1967), education is an activity to improve character (character, inner strength), mind, and body in harmony with nature and society.

Education is a barometer of the progress and civilization of a nation (Yusuf, 2018). According to Astawa (2017) in general, education aims to develop human potential in an integral, scientific, and sustainable manner so that humans can carry out their duties and obligations in life to achieve happiness in the present and the future. Therefore, education is the responsibility of the community and the government to form quality human resources.

The government as the implementer of education is obliged to provide education for all Indonesian citizens, as written in the 2003 National Education Law, which states that the central government and local governments have the right to direct, guide, assist, and supervise the implementation of education, and are obliged to provide services and facilities for the implementation of education. To improve the quality of human resources. This is stated in Article 31 of the 1945 Constitution, "every citizen has the right to education, has the right to attend compulsory education and the government is responsible for the education budget". The education budget given to Indonesian citizens is a minimum of 20% of the state and regional budget revenues. In addition to providing a budget for education, the Indonesian government also makes various efforts to improve the quality of education, such as curriculum development programs, textbook procurement programs, school operational assistance, school-based quality improvement management programs, teacher quality improvement programs, and the SMA Binaan Khusus.

All programs that have been implemented in the SMA Binaan Khusus have been evaluated by the research team using the CIPP evaluation model. The CIPP evaluation model aims to provide systematic and clear information to obtain a decision as a proactive evaluation from the start. Evaluation is a process of measuring and assessing and comparing a planned activity to achieve certain goals with the form of wise decisions that are by the existing reality (Arikunto, 2012; Stufflebeam & Shinkfield 2007; Tyler, 1950; Anderson & Ball 1978; Worthen & Sander 1979; Scriven, 1983). According to Aziz et al. (2018), the success of a program depends on the planning, implementation, and evaluation that will be carried out so that the objectives of the program can be achieved by expectations. According to Nurhayani et al. (2022), if the Education program has been implemented well, the program can be continued in the following year. If the education program is not implemented, a review and revision of the program must be carried out (Umam & Saripah 2018).

The results of the evaluation of the programs that have been carried out at the SMA Binaan Khusus show that (1) the SMA Binaan Khusus has made efforts to improve the quality of teaching and educational staff, (2) the SMA Binaan Khusus have made efforts to improve the standard of facilities and infrastructure, and (3) the SMA Binaan Khusus has carried out maximum student development. The SMA Binaan Khusus program is successful, it will be used as an example and reference for other schools in the city of Dumai as schools with an insight into excellence.

Similar studies have been carried out by several researchers, including 1) Grammatikopoulos (2012), Integrating program theory and systems-based procedures in program evaluation: a dynamic approach to evaluation educational program. 2) Rathbun et al. (2016) Evaluating the impact of an academic teacher development program: practical realities of an evidence-based study. 3) Wales (1987), Program evaluation: Some procedures from English in the workplace in Australia. 4) Borch et al. (2021) Student course evaluation documents: constituting evaluation practice. 5) Verwijnen et al. (2015) the evaluation system at the medical school of Maastricht.

The superiority of the school is related to the level of quality which means the degree of excellence of a product or service compared to others. According to Danin (2008) quality means the meaning of the degree (level) of the superiority of a product (work/effort) either in the form of goods or services, both tangible and intangible. The excellence of the school can be assessed by the quality of educational services at the school. Relatively speaking, educational services are said to be of high quality if they are by the standards set and can meet expectations and satisfy the users of the goods or services. Meanwhile, in absolute terms, educational services are said to be of high quality if they meet the best qualifications.

The quality of education can be seen from the input, process, and output of schools that meet the expectations of users of educational services at the school (Tayibnapis, 2008). Quality of education is the quality of various educational institution services to students and teaching staff by ensuring the availability of quality inputs for the occurrence of a quality educational process that will produce graduates as quality school outputs to meet expectations and satisfy users of educational services. According to Komariah & Triatna (2010), the quality of the school will be good if the school can provide services according to the needs of its customers.

Furthermore, according to Zazin (2011), school excellence can be seen from four dimensions, namely the quality of students, school curriculum, teacher quality, and equity as well as educational outcomes and processes. This is confirmed by Sagala (2009) that a superior school is where there are high academic standards for all subjects where students can achieve up to the specified standards as evidenced by test results with referenced procedures or other appropriate tests.

The criteria for a superior school according to Sagala (2009) are (1) quality, namely, the organization provides the highest quality of service provided by the organization to customers to ensure their satisfaction (2) growth, which ensures long-term growth and overall market growth. competitive (3) people, namely educational institutions guarantee the existence of the

people needed to carry out the vision and mission (4) ethical behavior (ethical conduct), namely the institution has rules that regulate consistent actions referring to quality as a standard the main growth of the organization and maximizing the values of achieving the vision and mission and (5) finance, namely the ability of the institution to maintain and manage budgets consistently as the main factor of growth and maximize user value.

Quality of education is the quality of various educational institution services to students and teaching staff by ensuring the availability of quality inputs for the occurrence of a quality educational process that will produce graduates as quality school outputs to meet expectations and satisfy users of educational services.

5. CONCLUSION

The results of the program evaluation that has been carried out at the SMA Binaan Khusus show that the SMA Binaan Khusus have implemented programs to improve the quality of teachers, the quality of adequate facilities, and infrastructure programs, and students who have the potential to be fostered and developed their programs. The programs at the SMA Binaan Khusus have been implemented well so that they can be used as examples and references for other schools in the city of Dumai as schools with excellent vision.

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